

The Modulatory Potential of Antioxidants Against Oxidative Stress in Autoimmune Disease

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Received: August 2021; Accepted: September 2021; Published online: October 2021

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Abstract

Free radicals and related compounds are commonly classified together as reactive oxygen species (ROS) to show their role in changing oxidative status within the cell. Cells commonly have different mechanisms to protect the body against damages created by free radicals. Problems are seen when synthesis of ROS is faster than their removal by the antioxidant protection mechanisms, or when the latter is impaired. This imbalance between cellular synthesis of ROS and the inability of cells to protect against them is known as oxidative stress (OS). OS can make cellular damage and then cell death due to the ROS oxidize cardinal cellular parts, such as lipids, proteins, and DNA. Antioxidants are exogenous (natural or synthetic) or endogenous factors play their role in several pathways including diminish of O₂, scavenging ROS or their precursors, suppressing their production and binding metal ions required for catalysis of ROS production. The natural antioxidant mechanism can be classified into two major types: enzymatic. The LMWA group of molecules can be more classified into directly-acting antioxidants and indirectly acting antioxidants. Therefore, in this study, we aimed to shed a light on the role of antioxidants in the management of autoimmune diseases.

Keywords: Antioxidants, autoimmunity, oxidative stress, multiple sclerosis, lichen planus, psoriasis, rheumatoid arthritis.

1. Introduction

A free radical is any chemical compounds that have one or more unpaired electrons. Unpaired electrons change the chemical function of an atom or molecule, commonly making it more reactive than the corresponding nonradical, due to its role as an electron acceptor and essentially “steals” electrons from other atoms (1, 2). This loss of electrons is called oxidation, and free radicals are known as oxidizing compounds since they tend to make other atoms to donate their electrons. We are constantly receive free radicals produced by electromagnetic radiation from the environment, both natural – (e. g., radon, cosmic radiation) and man-made (e. g., pollutants and cigarette smoke), and cellular metabolisms (e. g., respiratory burst, enzyme reactions) (3, 4). The most frequent cellular free radicals are hydroxyl radical ($\text{OH}\cdot$), superoxide radical ($\text{O}_2^{\cdot-}$), and nitric monoxide ($\text{NO}\cdot$). Other molecules, such as hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and peroxynitrite (ONOO^-), are not known as free radicals but can cause the production of free radicals through different chemical reactions (5). Free radicals and related compounds are commonly classified together as reactive oxygen species (ROS) to show their role in changing oxidative status within the cell (6). Cells commonly have different mechanisms to protect the body against damages created by free radicals. Problems are seen when synthesis of ROS is faster than their removal by the antioxidant protection mechanisms, or when the latter is impaired. This imbalance between cellular synthesis of ROS and the inability of cells to protect against them is known as oxidative stress (OS). OS can make cellular damage and then cell death due to the ROS oxidize cardinal cellular parts, such as lipids, proteins, and DNA (6, 7). Antioxidants are exogenous (natural or synthetic) or endogenous factors play their role in several pathways including diminish of O_2 , scavenging ROS or their precursors, suppressing their production and binding metal ions required for catalysis of ROS production. The natural antioxidant mechanism can be classified into two major types: enzymatic (e. g., catalase, superoxide dismutase,) and nonenzymatic or the low molecular weight antioxidants (LMWA). The LMWA group of molecules can be more classified into directly-acting antioxidants (e. g., scavengers and chain breaking antioxidants) and indirectly acting antioxidants (e. g., chelating agents). The former are considerably crucial in protection against OS, and most of them, including ascorbic and lipoic acids, polyphenols and carotenoids, are produced from dietary factors. The cell itself produces a minority of these molecules, such as glutathione and NADPH (5). Therefore, in this study, we aimed to shed a light on the role of antioxidants in the management of autoimmune diseases.

2. Multiple Sclerosis

2.1. Pathophysiology of Multiple Sclerosis

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is an autoimmune, chronic disease of the central nervous system (CNS), occurring commonly in late adolescence and early adult subjects and known by perivenous infiltration of lymphocytes and macrophages into the parenchyma of the CNS tissues. MS can manifest in different patterns including primary progressive (PPMS), relapsing progressive (RPMS), and secondary progressive phenotypes (SPMS) and relapsing remitting (RRMS), which is the most common type (80 % of patients) (8). Genetic risk factors such as interleukin-1 beta, interleukin-1 receptor, immunoglobulin Fc receptor genes, and apolipoprotein E (APO-E) gene have been proposed as having a substantial role in susceptibility to MS. HLA-DR2, which was suggested to increase the risk of susceptibility to MS, and DQ polymorphisms are not correlated with the course and severity of disease, despite their substantial role in disease susceptibility. Environmental risk factors such pathogens and chemicals and the high rate of MS in the northern hemisphere, have also been shown, and probably both genetic and environmental risk factors contribute to the pathogenesis of MS (9). The etiology of MS has not yet been fully understood, but it is well known that immunological factors are the most important in disease occurrence and progression (5, 8, 10, 11). It is well elucidated that pro-inflammatory mediators, such as interferon γ and tumor necrosis factor β (TNF- β) are secreted by activated TH-1 cells, may upregulate the expression of cell-surface markers on neighboring lymphocytes and antigen-presenting cells. Adherence of putative MS antigens, especially subunits of myelin such as myelin basic protein (MBP), myelin-associated basic glycoprotein (MOBP), myelin oligodendrocyte glycoprotein (MOG), proteolipid protein (PLP) and others by the trimolecular complex, the T-cell receptor (TCR) and major histocompatibility complex (MHC) class II molecules on antigen-presenting cells, may initiate either an increased immune reaction against the bound antigens or anergy. Therefore, autoantibodies against MBP and MOG have been shown in MS cases. Moreover, the autoimmune response, oligodendrocyte death, axon damage and even neuronal loss have also been shown to have role in the inflammatory mechanisms in the CNS (7, 8). The treatment of choice for acute attacks in MS is based upon high dose, short-term pulse treatment with corticosteroids and immunomodulatory therapies such as interferon beta-1a and -1b, glatiramer acetate (copaxone®), and mitoxantrone. Furthermore, immunosuppression treatment with choices such as azathioprine, cyclophosphamide, intravenous immune globulin (IVIG) and more treatments such as Plasmapheresis have also been recommended. Other novel therapies needing the assessment of larger, placebo controlled studies are estriol, statins and natalizumab, which is an $\alpha 4$ integrin antagonist. Despite new evidences in MS pharmacotherapy, not all cases with MS show acceptable response to treatment with these treatments, probably due to the disease heterogeneity. Investigations of subjects with SPMS have showed inconsistent findings and, so far, there have been no positive phase III studies of immunomodulatory treatment in subjects with PPMS (5, 8, 9).

1.2. Oxidative Stress and Excitotoxicity

Although different risk factors can have a role in initiating OS in cells, the neurotransmitter, glutamate, is the major trigger of this mechanism in the brain, primarily through motivation of its ionotropic receptors. Glutamate and related excitatory amino acids play the most important role in activation of the excitatory synaptic function in the mammalian CNS and are secreted by an approximately 40 % of all synapses (5, 8, 12, 13). Ionotropic receptors can be detected

by their pharmacological and electrophysiological characteristics: the N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA), which is the main glutamate receptor, α -amino-3-hydroxy-5-methyl-4-isoxasole-propionic acid (AMPA) and the kainic acid (KA) receptors (6, 12). The calcium-mediated features of glutamate receptor function, causing neuronal degeneration, may involve a number of different mechanisms leading to OS. Free radical related damage can be made by the activation of phospholipase A2 (PLA2) and the following secretion of amino acids, which with oxygen radicals increase the secretion of glutamate, thereby initiating a vicious process (6, 12).

1.3. Role of Excitotoxic Damage in the Neurological Deficits in EAE

In-vitro investigations propose that glutamate, the major excitatory neurotransmitter in the mammalian brain, contributes to MS pathophysiology. It was shown that oligodendrocytes, the myelin-producing cell of the CNS, are highly sensitive to glutamate excitotoxicity, commonly by the AMPA/kainate receptors, which have higher permeability to Ca^{2+} . Moreover, demyelinating plaques induced by excitotoxins can be similar to those seen in MS, leading to histologically similar impairments (14, 15). Previous experimental investigations revealed that therapies with AMPA/kainate antagonists yielded significant improvement of experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis (EAE), the commonly approved animal model for the investigation of MS that has different clinical and pathological characteristics of MS (7, 8). The AMPA/kainate antagonists also enhanced oligodendrocyte survival and decreased dephosphorylation of neurofilament H, an indicator of axonal impairment. In one of these investigations, mice were induced EAE following transfer of lymph node cells activated by myelin basic protein. The amelioration in the clinical status seen in these cases following administration of an AMPA/kainate receptor antagonist associated with an enhancement in oligodendrocyte survival and decreased axonal impairment (8, 9). However, these beneficial roles were shown at an early phases of the disease course, which does not commonly involve demyelination. Another investigation, used the Lewis rat model of acute EAE, in which little demyelination is seen, and also the chronic EAE model. In both models, the secondary degeneration of spinal cord motor neurons, seen as a result of the loss of white matter, was considerably decreased following treatment with glutamate receptor antagonists (14, 15). Interestingly, neuronal versus oligodendroglial death and axonal loss were not assessed simultaneously and no investigation of demyelination was performed. Therefore, the putative role of each type of impairment to the clinical status cannot be evaluated. Nevertheless, these results open up new avenues for the amelioration of autoimmune demyelination, such as riluzole, an antagonist of glutamate neurotransmission as a treatment suggested for amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) (5, 8). However, recently it has been shown that riluzole, used before and even after the presence of clinical signs, significantly decreased the clinical symptoms, inflammation, demyelination and axonal impairment of MOG-induced EAE model. Similar with this possibility, the neurological deficit due to EAE has commonly been decreased by treatments to decrease the level of ROS. There is also findings in MS of an enhancement in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) levels of glutamate in correlation with the severity and phase of the disease and that glutamate synthesis by macrophages may contribute to axonal impairment and oligodendrocytes death in MS plaques (14, 15). A potential cellular factors that could have role in increased glutamate levels in CSF is sensitized microglia, which are increased during immunological damages and inflammation. These cells, in cultures exposed to high potassium,

can secrete glutamate by reverse glutamate transport, a mechanism that is potentiated under pathological status. OS might also have role in the enhancement in glutamate level in the extracellular space by decreasing the efficiency of glutamate transporters (5, 8, 9, 14-16).

1.4. Antioxidants in the Treatment of EAE and Multiple Sclerosis

The main challenge in treatment of neurodegenerative disorders, including MS, is to passage substances into the brain through the BBB, which is the major protection that separates the brain microenvironment from the blood within the cerebrovascular tree. This protection decreases the efficacy of many agents, including antioxidants, owing to their limited introduction to the brain through the BBB. Therefore, production of novel antioxidants that make BBB transport possible will related to new findings of BBB features and transport mechanisms (8, 9, 17-19).

The encouraging results with antioxidants in in-vitro investigations resulted in their evaluation in experimental studies of MS. In a recent study, it has been shown that the antioxidant tirilazade mesylate, a member of the lazaroids family which were suggested to remove lipid peroxy radicals and suppress iron-dependent lipid peroxidation, was effective in decreasing the incidence and severity of actively-induced EAE (18). Another investigation revealed that oral treatment with the oxidant-scavenger N-acetylcysteine (NAC), which can effectively increase intracellular glutathione concentrations, suppressed the initiation of acute EAE (8, 20). The protection was correlated with increase of the specific lymphocyte proliferative reaction to the immunizing antigens (spinal cord homogenate) at early phases, post encephalitogenic injection. Another study revealed that intra-peritoneal treatment with catalase before the initiation of neurological impairment delayed the manifestation of EAE and decreased its severity and duration. Moreover, butylated hydroxyanisole, another LMWA, was effective in decreasing the incidence, severity and mortality of passively occurred EAE (8, 18). A synthetic salen-manganese complex, Euk-8, may be known as a prototype molecule of a new class of synthetic catalytic scavengers with combined SOD and catalase function, was also suggested to improve EAE in animal models. The authors revealed that repeated injection of Euk-8 initiated at the time of EAE induction delayed the initiation and considerably decreased the severity of the disease. Furthermore, all Euk-8-treated mice completely ameliorated following 40 days. Furthermore, the authors revealed that subsequent to the treatment with Euk-8, 4 days after EAE presentation, also yielded a significant improvement of EAE. Recently, it was revealed that alpha lipoic acid a well-known antioxidant, found in the diet and capable of passage through the BBB, decreased severity of EAE in mice (8, 9). It was revealed that alpha lipoic acid had dose-dependent decrease in the 10-day cumulative disease severity, and suppressed inflammation, demyelination and axonal impairment in the spinal cord. Furthermore, there was a significant decrease in CD3 + T cells and CD11b + monocyte/macrophage cells within the SC, and suppression of matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9) function in a dose-dependent fashion. The conclusion of the study was that alpha lipoic acid inhibited EAE may by decreasing T cell passage into the spinal cord, may by the suppression of MMP- 9 function (18, 20). Current findings from experimental studies show that consumption of N-acetylcysteine amide (AD4), our novel BBB-penetrating low-molecular antioxidant, prior or even following the emergence of symptoms, significantly decreased the

clinical severity of MOG-induced EAE C3H.SW mice. Furthermore, it also decreased inflammation, axonal impairment and suppressed MMP 9 function probably in a process that involves, at least in part, macrophage-induced ROS suppression (5, 8, 18). Several studies have revealed that suppression of the inducible/inflammatory form of iNOS, as well as the use of anti-sense knockdown of iNOS, inhibit EAE animal model of MS. Furthermore, it has been shown that the suppression of iNOS, or scavenging of NO \cdot or peroxynitrite by uric acid, suppressed neurological impairments in animal model with EAE, while withdrawal of iNOS inhibitor caused the presentation of neurological symptoms within one day. In contrast, recent evidence revealed that suppression of NO synthesis is lethal. Therefore, it is still not understood whether NO suppression is beneficial in treating animal model of MS (8, 9, 17, 20, 21).

1.5. Clinical Trials

Following the encouraging results in the EAE models, many investigators have showed that dietary antioxidant consumption i.e. vitamin E or selenium may have a role in inhibition of disease progression. Moreover, it has been revealed that administration of antioxidants (6.6 mg. of sodium selenite, 2 gm of vitamin C and 500 I. U. of vitamin E per day) enhanced and normalized the glutathione peroxidase function and the cellular content of linoleic acid in erythrocytes and hematogenous cells within 3 weeks, with no effect on MS severity. However, despite media findings in subjects who appear to benefit from following restrictive regimens, there is minimal scientific findings that antioxidant intake has beneficial role in slowing the rate or severity of MS. Only two investigations of mild to severely disabled cases have been carried out to date, showing that the severity of MS disability did not associate considerably with intake of specific diets. The clarification of the study for this finding was that subjects with severe disability or poor care support would be unlikely to cooperate in such investigations (8, 9, 17, 18, 20).

3. Oral Lichen Planus

3.1. Pathophysiology of Oral Lichen Planus

Oral lichen planus (OLP) is a chronic disease with the major role of immune system. Since OLP is an immune-related disease, stress and anxiety and other risk factors in association with immune system can be causative risk factors which probably initiate the disease. This disease dominantly is seen in women and involves 2-5% of the people. Furthermore, its possible manifestation is in the decade 4-5 of life (22-25). The exact cause of OLP has not been introduced, and it is mostly known as a complex disease with different risk factors such as mechanical, electrochemical, trauma and psychological, infectious, malnutrition, stress, overworking, mucous exciting triggers and allergy, endocrine disorders, salivary gland disorders, genetic susceptibility and immunological illnesses. Hydropic production of the basal epithelial cells (keratinocytes), an intraepithelial and dense subepithelial lymphocytic infiltration of mononuclear cells and epithelial invasion are histological features of OLP (7, 23-26). Appearance of initial precursors are primary causatives for developing oral malignancy that oral leukoplakia and submucous fibrosis are two major precancerous manifestations among them, which 8-10% of these lesions become finally malignant (22, 23, 25). The World Health Organization (WHO) classified OLP as a potential premalignant disorder suggesting its

potentiality to convert into squamous cell carcinoma. Recent study revealed OLP occurrence through both of antigen-specific and non-specific processes. In antigen-specific process, basal keratinocytes introduce antigen and antigen-specific keratinocyte are removed by CD8+ cytotoxic T lymphocytes. In non-specific processes, mast cell degranulates and matrix metalloproteinase initiates in OLP lesions. OLP is a T-cell mediated inflammatory disorder (24-26). Through mast cell/T-cell interactions in OLP plaques, mast cell secreted mediators, chemokines and matrix metalloproteinases can trigger T-cell activation, migration, production and differentiation. The clinical manifestation of OLP involves a wide ranges from asymptomatic white keratotic plaques to painful erosions and ulcerations with six distinctive clinical subtypes: Keratotic reticular, papular, plaque-like white patches, erosive, atrophic, and bullous (ulcerative) (22-25). The epidemiologic distribution of plaques differs in each geographical parts, as the majority of the lesions in Iran were reported reticular (66%), but commonly, the most frequent are reticular and erosive type. The first three types are commonly present minor or no symptoms without any complaints that is, painless, with no need for any intervention or therapy, but cases should be assessed on time with a suggested follow-up visits every 4–6 months or sooner if any symptom is seen. On the other hand, the erosive, atrophic, and ulcerative plaques, that are surrounded by keratotic types propose an impaired epithelium, a painful and/or a burning sensation at the oral mucosa, and therefore interfere with eating, speaking, and swallowing (23-25). Oral pain caused by OLP may be seen from a little bothersome to annoying pain that can suppress cases from their daily activity. It can remain in some cases for a long time, but a spontaneous amelioration of the atrophic plaques is often seen. Many investigations have been carried out, focusing on OLP with different point of views; pathologically and therapeutically. In the present review, we aimed to summarize both pathologic and therapeutic advances in this topic with respect to the importance of biomarkers for OLP diagnosis, OLP association with other disorders, and more effective interventions on OLP (22, 24, 26).

3.2. Antioxidants and Oral Lichen Planus

It has been demonstrated that in cases with OLP the mean levels of salivary peroxidation results such as malonaldehyde (MDA) and 8-hydroxydeoxyguanosine (8-OHdG) enhanced and that of antioxidants such as vitamin C and E decreased in comparison with control healthy subjects. After treatment with curcumin, for more than two hundred days, the level of peroxidation products (oxidants) decreased and that of antioxidants enhanced. Therefore, level of vitamin C and E, as antioxidants, might be an appropriate biomarkers to estimate precancerous status similar to OLP (17, 22-24).

Furthermore, investigations have shown the existence of serum anti-gastric parietal cell autoantibody (GPCA) in several different populations of OLP cases. Group of GPCA-positive OLP has signs and symptoms of oral lichen planus in types of reticular, erosive or ulcerative oral mucosal plaques and pain or burning sensation of lesional oral mucosa. Moreover, treatment of OLP cases with levamisole in addition to vitamin B12 revealed a significant decrease in GPCA level. This decrease in GPCA level was in line with improvement of buccal mucosa plaques. As a result, GPCA level of serum is a potential diagnostic marker for oral lesion planus (22-24).

Antioxidant systems prevent the production of ROSs, block their function or act as scavengers for free radicals. On the other hand, antioxidant mechanisms repair the changes caused by the action of ROSs in different cellular components; therefore, DNA damage is improved through enzymes, oxidized proteins are removed by the proteolytic systems, and phospholipases and acyltransferases repair the oxidized lipids. It has been shown that the low level of antioxidants may be observed as a risk factor for the occurrence of OLP. Most of the investigations included in this study have focused on introducing antioxidant biomarkers in order to evaluate the imbalance between prooxidants and antioxidants (22-24). Enzymatic antioxidants (superoxide dismutase-SOD, catalase-CAT, glutathione peroxidase-GPX) were more commonly assessed. SOD and CAT enzymes were investigated in LP patients' serum and in erythrocytes and as well as in LP plaques. In all investigations that evaluated SOD function, enhanced function was detected. Contrarily, CAT function was lower, and GPX function was lower, or no significant differences were found in comparison with the controls. These findings reveal the imbalance of antioxidant mechanisms. CAT is the main enzyme that has a role in the removal of H₂O₂; thus, in the context of low levels of CAT and high levels of SOD that converts the superoxide anion into H₂O₂, there is an excessive levels of H₂O₂, which will result in the vacuolization of basal cells in LP plaques (22-24). With respect to non-enzymatic antioxidants, in all investigations, decreased or similar levels were detected in CLP cases in comparison with the controls. Another significant part of the antioxidant mechanisms is the uric acid that can remove ROSs and bind metal ions that will not be able any longer to catalyze different ROS-producing process. The plasma levels of antioxidant products such as GPX, vitamin C, selenium, bilirubin, and uric acid have been assessed in cases with CLP and healthy people and has shown considerable differences between the two groups only for vitamin C. A clarification could be the fact that vitamin C is water-soluble and shows one of the primary antioxidants against OS. The investigators showed that vitamin C supplements may be effective in the treatment of CLP (22-24).

4. Psoriasis

4.1. Pathophysiology of Psoriasis

Chronic inflammation known as different types of pathophysiological dysregulations which eventually cause a sustained, increased synthesis of pro-inflammatory mediators and OS. In recent years, different investigations have assessed the correlation between the inflammatory mechanism and the development of chronic, non-communicable diseases (NCD), such as obesity, diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular disorders, cancer and autoinflammatory disorders such as rheumatoid arthritis and psoriasis. Apart from genetic and environmental risk factors, nutrition has introduced as a potential intervention on immunological and inflammatory mechanisms (27, 28). Dietary regimens, such as the Mediterranean diet, which include a high consumption of fruits and vegetables and a low proportion of fat and sugars, have been suggested to manage chronic inflammation and decrease the incidence of NCD. However, as every diet contain many different nutrients from different food products, extensive investigation has been performed on the specific nutrients that constitute an everyday dietary regimen, which include macronutrients, namely proteins, fats and carbohydrates, and micronutrients, such as vitamins, trace elements and antioxidants such as polyphenols and

carotenoids, which, in turn, can have a different effects depending both on their daily intake and food origin. Psoriasis is one of the most common autoinflammatory disorders in the world, with an incidence of 2–3% in Europe and North America (27, 29, 30). Its pathophysiology is noted multifactorial, and it is known by the dysregulation of the innate and adaptive immune systems, with the sensitization of T helper (Th)-1 and Th-17 T cells causing an enhanced synthesis of inflammatory mediators such as interleukins (IL) IL-1, IL-6, IL-23, IL-22, IL-17, and IL-33, tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), and interferon-gamma (IFN- γ) (26, 28). In this process, inflammation has a pivotal role by initiating hyper-synthesis and angiogenesis, causing the common skin plaques and the articular involvement of psoriatic arthritis (7, 27, 30). Since the report by Späh, where the idea of a potential common inflammatory mechanism between psoriasis and atherosclerosis was first proposed, the association between psoriasis and chronic inflammation has been noted in many investigations. As inflammation is regulated by nutrition, it comes as no surprise that the effects of diet on the incidence and severity of the disease as well as on treatment intervention has been a matter of extensive investigation. In this study, the role of macro- and micronutrients in inflammation and immunity will be summarized. Then, we state the most recent evidence on the effects of obesity on psoriatic disease, and whether and how different dietary compounds and food components may show beneficial in the treatment of the disease and emerge as possible therapeutic interventions along with the conventional pharmacologic interventions (27-29).

4.2. Antioxidants and Psoriasis

Micronutrients are essential elements which are detected in very small quantities in the human body and include vitamins, minerals and trace elements. They are removers of ROS and they can inhibit the production of free radicals and inflammatory mediators, serving as potent antioxidants. Below, research evidence regarding the role of the main micronutrients in inflammation is stated (17, 27-29).

4.3. Polyphenols and Psoriasis

Polyphenols are the most common antioxidants in diet, with their main sources being fruits, vegetables, red wine, nuts, green tea, and olive oil. Many investigations have shown the beneficial impact of a diet rich in polyphenol sources on inflammation and human health status. In 24 obese cases, the intake of 46 g of grape powder for 3 weeks caused an important decrease in low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) and cholesterol levels and increased immune activity, and a similar finding was reported in an another investigation with the consumption of apple or apple pomace. Intake of cooked purple potato (200 g/day containing 288 mg anthocyanins) for 14 days decreased pulse wave velocity, an indicator of endothelial dysfunction, in comparison with white potato in healthy subjects (27-29). In 62 cases with at least one cardiovascular disease (CVD) factor, intake of 330 mL/day bilberry juice yielded a decrease in CRP, IL-6 and IL-15 levels. In women with metabolic syndrome, the intake of freeze-dried strawberries (FDS) for 8 weeks reduced LDL and vascular cell adhesion molecule 1 (VCAM-1), and similar were the findings in another study with T2DM female cases (26, 30, 31). Since vegetables are also rich in other compounds, such as vitamins and fiber, some investigations in animal studies have used purified polyphenol extracts to show their role more specifically. Polyphenol extracts of the sea buckthorn berry was used to rats fed a high-fat diet

(HFD), decreasing TNF- α , IL-6, endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS), ICAM-1 and lipid levels. A diet enriched with 1% blueberry decreased aortic atherosclerotic plaques regions in ApoE^{-/-} mice, with a concomitant enhancement in the antioxidant capacity of superoxide dismutase (SOD) 1, SOD2 and GRx (enzymes which catalyze the dismutation of the superoxide radical) and decreased lipid peroxidation (27-29). Resveratrol, a flavonoid commonly detected in red wine, reduces the level of TNF- α by producing SIRT-1 (initiating autophagy), eNOS (increasing NO synthesis), and Nrf2 (preventing the NF- κ B mechanism and proinflammatory cytokine synthesis) mechanisms, decreases the production of ICAM-1 and VCAM-1 via suppression of the NF- κ B pathway activation and decreases the production of foam cells via suppression of NADPH oxidase-1 in mouse macrophages. Quercetin, a flavonol detected in sources such as red onions, capers, apples and nuts, decreases inflammation and OS in human and animal studies. Pathways include decrease of the production of foam cells by enhancement of the expression of PPAR-receptors and ATP-binding cassette transporter (ABCA1), inhibiting of leukocyte recruitment and reducing the synthesis of Th-1 derived IFN- γ , among others (27, 29). Curcumin, a flavonoid that is commonly detected in turmeric, curry spice, and ginger, has been revealed to reduce SOD, malondialdehyde (MDA) and CRP in cases with metabolic syndrome and IL-1 β , TNF- α , ICAM-1 and VCAM-1 in mice, through the suppression of the TLR4 signaling mechanism. However, a important disadvantage of the aforementioned investigations is that the beneficial findings were provided at therapeutically doses that highly exceed normal daily food consumption, a fact which renders the efficacy of antioxidants in everyday clinical practice questionable. Another food source rich in phenolic components is olive oil, which is a basic part of Mediterranean diet. Its anti-inflammatory characteristics are known not only due to its favorable lipid profile, with oleic acid being its major fraction (55–83%), but also due to its minor components, with the phenols oleuropein and hydroxytyrosol standing out nutritionally (27-30, 32). The beneficial impact of olive oil and, especially, extra virgin olive oil (EVOO) has been shown in a number of reports. In blood platelets taken from 5 healthy people, the consumption of 0.2 mg/mL EVOO with or without catalase decreased the speed of Nox2 and H₂O₂ synthesis. In 33 hypercholesterolemic cases, EVOO enriched with polyphenols caused an enhancement in HDL and antioxidant characteristic, and in cells of cases with ulcerative colitis, cells triggered with 3 mM oleuropein showed decreased synthesis of TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-17 and COX-2. In subjects with abnormal fasting glucose receiving a daily meal containing 10 g EVOO, postprandial circulating LPS stabilized, along with the oxidation of LDL and NADPH oxidase 2 (Nox2). In a sub-investigation related to the Prevención con Dieta Mediterránea (PREDIMED) study, subjects receiving Mediterranean diet plus EVOO revealed a decrease in IL-6, VCAM-1, ICAM-1 and LDL, and an increase in HDL. Similar findings were reported in investigations regarding the correlation of olive oil with cardiovascular disorders, as well as in animal studies. The phenolic compounds in EVOO are capable of diminishing LDL oxidization and possess potent antioxidant properties, with oleuropein also having anti-proliferative properties (27-32).

4.4. Carotenoids and Psoriasis

Carotenoids are commonly detected in fruits, vegetables, bacteria and fungi, with the most significant being carotenes and xanthophylls. Carotenoids play their role primarily as potent antioxidants, can quench radicals and singlet oxygen, interact with nuclear receptors

RAR/RXR (retinoic acid receptor/retinoid X receptor) to strengthen immune mechanisms, and suppress the pro-inflammatory NF- κ B pathway. In a clinical trial on nonobese humans, consumption of astaxanthin (a xanthophyll found mainly in seafood) for three months improved HDL-C, TG, and adiponectin levels (27, 29, 30, 33). In cases with peripheral artery disease, consumption of orange and blackcurrant juice for one month caused a decrease in CRP and plasma fibrinogen; in a similar way, MDA and 8,12-isoprostane F2a-VI levels were inversely correlated with levels of individual carotenoids. Lutein, detected commonly in broccoli and spinach, has a beneficial effect on arterial stiffness and decreases IL-6, TNF- α and prostaglandin E2 (PGE2). Beta-carotene, detected commonly in carrots and tomatoes, decreases the synthesis of IL-1 β and VCAM-1 in LDL receptor knockout mice. On the other hand, positive correlations between lycopene and F2-isoprostane or MDA concentrations have been reported in large-scale human investigations, which were related to the fact that lycopene consumption came commonly from pasta sauce, ketchup and fast-food intake and not from tomatoes, its major natural source (29, 33). In cases with cystic fibrosis, beta-carotene reduced MDA concentrations at the dose of 1 mg/kg/d, but not at 10 mg/d. In an investigation with healthy people receiving 5, 10, 20 or 40 mg/d beta-carotene for 5 weeks, MDA was decreased only in the highest group, while in another study, consumption of either 15 or 120 mg/d beta-carotene caused similar decrease in lipid peroxide concentration. In conclusion, findings from large-scale studies about the clinical importance of carotenoids remains contradicting (27-30).

4.5. Vitamins and Psoriasis

Vitamin A found in both plants (carrots and red peppers) as carotenoids and in eggs, liver and milk as retinol, with both types being metabolized to its effective form, which is retinoic acid. Retinoic acid initiates phagocytosis and sensitization of natural killer (NK) T-cells and, therefore, vitamin A deficiency has been correlated with defective immune reactions. Vitamin C is a potent ROS scavenger and triggers neutrophil apoptosis and T-cell maturation, and its increased dietary consumption has been correlated with lower concentrations of CRP and PAI-1 (27, 29, 34). Vitamin C is also indispensable for the antioxidant properties of vitamin E, which has a role in T-cell and NK cells function. In humans, vitamin E consumption has been revealed to decrease pro-inflammatory mediators IL-1 β , IL-6 and TNF- α by triggering the synthesis of cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP). Vitamins C and E are correlated with a decrease in coronary artery disease, but their consumption in high pharmacological doses seems to have no additional advantage. Despite being best renowned for its characteristics in calcium homeostasis, vitamin D also has immunomodulatory properties, with calcitriol being necessary for T-cells activity. In vitro investigations revealed that vitamin D3 can cause reduced expression of CD40, CD80, and CD86, and increased IL-10 production (27, 28, 34, 35). However, in the VITAL investigation, where vitamin D3 (cholecalciferol) and n-3 FAs were supplemented in 25,871 cases with a median follow-up of 5.3 years, no differences in the incidence of invasive cancer or cardiovascular disorders were reported in comparison with the placebo group. Another issue regarding vitamin D is the fact that its plasma concentrations are affected by different factors. Higher levels of sun exposure have been correlated with a lower risk of vitamin D deficiency; on the other hand, more sun exposure is the primary risk factor for skin cancer and commonly seems to have a detrimental impact on many cutaneous disorders such as psoriasis (29, 35, 36). Therefore, the appropriate level of sun exposure to maintain a

sufficient vitamin D level is yet to be determined, while a number of other factors such as alcohol consumption, physical function and genetic polymorphisms play a pivotal role; in fact, diet seems to be of little importance. Finally, with respect to the B-complex vitamins, a high B6 consumption was reversely correlated with plasma CRP. In cases with B12 deficiency, methylcobalamin consumption improved the CD4/CD8 ratio and inhibited NK cell function. It has been revealed that consumption of 5 mg/d of folic acid and 1 mg/d of B12 (typical daily consumption: about 500 mcg/day and 3.4 mcg/day, respectively) for two months considerably ameliorated endothelial dilatation, and a similar findings were also approved in a 7-year clinical trial where this combination along with high doses of B6 was performed. However, such high doses which cannot readily be used in everyday practice doubt the clinical importance of these findings (27-30, 34-36).

4.6. Trace Elements and Psoriasis

Selenium exerts its antioxidant characteristics through its roles in antioxidant enzymes functions called selenoproteins, including glutathione peroxidase (GPx), selenoprotein P, and thioredoxin reductase. Despite, however, having an important role in the improvement of the immune system, investigations have not approved that consumption of selenium reduces the risk for cardiovascular mortality (27, 34). On the other hand, research evidence regarding zinc seem to be more consistent. Apart from its role in T-cell function, zinc is a cofactor in a range of antioxidant enzymes, especially SOD and the anti-inflammatory SMAD proteins. Low levels of zinc make increased OS in endothelial cells *in vitro*; *in vivo*, consumption of zinc in diabetic mice decreased aortic tunica media thickness, VCAM-1 and PAI-1, and increased the synthesis of Nrf2 and metallothioneins in the aorta, both being powerful antioxidants. Once again, however, it should be considered that the doses consumed were extremely higher than the common daily consumption (27-30, 34).

5. Rheumatoid Arthritis

5.1. Pathophysiology of Rheumatoid Arthritis

Recently, rheumatoid arthritis (RA) vaults into one of the most common diseases which affects 0.5–1% of people all over the world and bring economic burden for both cases and society. However, current medical interventions only provide symptomatic amelioration but fail to cure it completely or suppress this progression. RA is a complex systemic disease that could be correlated with different cell types and cytokines. Autoantibodies are the triggers for RA pathological commencement and self-resistance is the characteristic feature (37, 38). The continuous deterioration of cells and tissues involves main organs, finally to make the occurrence of degenerative diseases similar to the degenerative characteristics of RA. It is well understood that RA marks a chronic autoimmune disorder known by joint inflammation causing progressive cartilage impairment and bone erosion and also noted with degenerative presentations such as cell death and the abnormal bone formation initiated by homeostasis loss of bone metabolism. The incentive of cell death in chondrocytes triggers the mechanism of RA and reverse of this disparity that captures different considerations for the treatment of RA (7, 38, 39). Lipid peroxidation-related ferroptosis is known as a new and non-apoptotic cell death introduced in several years ago, which has been widely investigated during the nearly past

years. Recently, several investigations have shown the correlation between ferroptosis and degenerative or tumor-related disorders. Degenerative characteristics seem to be initiated by disorder overwhelmingly when repairing peroxidized lipids, which eventually causing cell death. Therefore, ferroptosis may act as the tumor inhibitor or degenerative disorder trigger in removing cells that lack access to seize important nutrients surrounding, hereof, chondrocyte death in RA that may be bound up with it. Hitherto, the bulk of investigations proposed that ferroptosis can initiate degenerative mechanisms and plays a pivotal role, while the underlying process is still poorly known, whereas regulation of ferroptosis is a potential treatment (38, 39). Suppressors of ferroptosis can protect brain from degenerative diseases and other neurodegeneration syndromes or traumatic and hemorrhagic brain impairments. Besides, in some other tissues or diseases, such as liver hemochromatosis, these suppressors also perform with activities. Ferroptosis may have a role in the degenerative mechanism of RA progression hereof. And, to date, ferroptosis suppressor-protein 1 (FSP1) is newly corroborated with the ability of antagonizing the mechanism of ferroptosis and it may be exploited as the therapeutic goal of treatment for RA. Ferroptosis is regarded as the newly known cell death type that has been introduced and growing rapidly with its compensations by more investigations. Keeping in mind that RA is endowed with its poorly underlying process and causes torments for involved cases, novel investigation approaches may be of significance to receive expectations hopefully (4, 39, 40).

5.2. ROS and Lipid Peroxidation in Rheumatoid Arthritis

In synovial fluid, the extracellular secretion of ROS opposites to antioxidants increase the speed of the development of atherosclerosis in RA. Generally, ROS could oxidize low density lipoproteins (LDLs) that augment mediators, adhesion molecules, and glycation end-products to increase inflammatory mechanism. Furthermore, monocytes forming foam cells phagocytose these in the synovium and synovial fluid of the RA (3, 6, 41). Immunoglobulins with glycooxidation secrete glycation end-products which are associated with RA and systemic inflammatory response. Furthermore, there are also some reports showing that ROS oxidize autoreactivity to type II collagen in early stages of RA and when endogenous secretory receptors of advanced glycation end-products target bone which could be considered to treat RA potentially. Advanced oxidation protein products (AOPPs) have role in mechanism of different inflammatory with Nox-dependent ROS and are accumulated in RA. Moreover, ROS deteriorates both extra- and intracellular matrix such as proteoglycans, which are vital for chondrocytes. Proteoglycans and collagen in extracellular matrix could be regulated by ROS in the structure and activity through oxidation and nitrosylation, which is similar to cellular substances. Furthermore, proteoglycan core protein would be affected when effecting the hyaluronan-binding region (6, 41). It was determined that O₂ radicals (O₂·) inhibit the synthesis of the type II collagen and sulfation of glycosaminoglycans and then cause the fragmentation of the chondroitin sulfate and hyaluronan, with similarity to higher fibril cross-linking and lower degree of collagen fragmentation. In terms of cartilage damage, ROS dampens the reaction between growth factors and chondrocyte that finally cause the apoptosis of chondrocyte. Tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) can stimulate the BH3 domain-only member of the Bcl2 family Bid and trigger ROS production with NADPH oxidase at the cell surface (42, 43). Therefore, phospholipids are oxidized to hydroperoxides by ROS, which are

fragments and make truncated phospholipids. With the initiation of TNF- α binding to TNF receptor, oxidative fragmented phospholipids reversibly affect mitochondria, then secrete cytochrome c (Cyt c), and produce a functional apoptosome to improve cytotoxicity via caspase activation. However, glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4) repulses this mechanism, mitigates lipid hydroperoxides, and suppresses peroxidized phospholipid production so that it inhibits cell death. Furthermore, ROS-induced peroxidation could be suppressed by antioxidants. The superoxide dismutase 3 (SOD3) catalyzes the mechanisms and transformations of the superoxide to decrease the superoxidation. The serum membrane-bound NADPH oxidase (NOX) produces the intra- and extra-cellular $O_2^{\cdot-}$ whereas SOD3 converts the superoxide into hydrogen peroxide and oxygen molecules. Furthermore, extracellular H_2O_2 is transferred into the cell through aquaporin channels and transformed into water via catalase (CAT), peroxiredoxin (PRX), and GPX. In inflammation, SOD3 can suppress the mechanism by both reducing ROS and affecting cellular signals including decreasing pro-inflammatory mediators (IL-1 β , IL-2, IL-4, IFN- γ , and TNF- α) and secreting matrix metalloproteinase (MMP-2, MMP-3, and MMP-9) secretion in synovial fluid. Moreover, SOD3 suppresses ROS-induced DNA impairment and modulate expression of redox-sensitive genes (4, 41, 42).

5.3. ROS and Signaling Pathways in Rheumatoid Arthritis

In RA, ROS cases in MAPKs, PI3K-Akt, and NF- κ B signaling mechanisms for both T cell tolerance and cellular signaling transduction. The c-Jun N-terminal kinases (JNK) and extracellular signal-related kinases (ERK1/2) have role in initiating cascades as major mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK). The Rac directly triggers membrane-bound NADPH oxidase or by the Ras mechanism and produces $O_2^{\cdot-}$ (3, 6, 44). The product superoxide or H_2O_2 initiates JNK cascade reaction by successively affecting Rac, MEK1/4, MEK4/7, and JNK that ultimately action intra-nuclear c-jun, hints on that superoxide that plays its role in ERK1/2 cascade pathway. Furthermore, the product ROS causes matrix degradation, cell death, and then inflammation in cartilage, and the initiation of RA would be accelerated. In addition, ROS could enhance Akt downstream mechanism due to its correlation with PI3K signaling activation. However, ROS inactivates Akt by phosphatase that suppresses PIP3 production and phosphorylates and degrades PTEN via casein kinase II degrading suppressing tensin homolog (PTEN) (6, 44). Commonly, Akt/PKB is inhibited by ROS via inactivating protein phosphatase 2A (PP2A), but when ROS in lower level, ROS oxidizes disulfide bridges in Akt/PKB to stimulate PP2A to bind Akt/PKB, thus make Akt/ PKB active and sustain for short time. Non-canonical NF- κ B mechanism is correlated with IKK α and the proteolysis of NF- κ B2/p100 precursor that activates NF- κ B2/RelB. NF- κ B-inducing kinase (NIK) can be activated by OS and the ROS affects tumor necrosis factor receptor-associated factor 3 (TRAF3), uncouples, and accumulates NIK. In non-canonical NF- κ B mechanism, NIK activity matters and accelerates NF- κ B2/p100 processing by phosphorylation and ubiquitylation of I κ B kinase α (IKK α), inducing p52 production and the nuclear translocation of p52 and RelB. ROS inhibits the oxidation reduction of cysteine residues and phosphatases to make NIK active in the non-canonical mechanism. The antioxidant product in the NF- κ B mechanism could be activated to affect ROS. Meanwhile, iron channels have also role in RA pathogenesis. Hypotonic synovial fluid has role in RA development; besides, transient receptor potential vanilloid 4 (TRPV4)

links to ATP secretion as a Ca²⁺-permeable channel. It is determined that hypotonicity of synovial fluid evokes Ca²⁺ entry via activating TRPV4 channel, which improves the procedure ATP secretion and production of ROS, then exacerbates the propagation of synovial fibroblasts (4, 44, 45).

5.4. Effectiveness of Phytomolecules in Rheumatoid Arthritis

As explained, RA is responsible for important human morbidity and burden in modern life. OS is known as a potential biomarker for diagnosis of disease pathophysiology in cases with RA. Th1 and Th2 mediators balance attract the great consideration as clarified earlier. The degree of polarization and heterogeneity of mononuclear T lymphocytes or polymorphonuclear neutrophils may be pivotal in the suppression and continuing of inflammation in RA (3, 46). Therefore, the investigations on non-toxic natural antioxidants are of great consideration now a days. 5-Hydroxy-3, 40, 7-trimethoxyflavone: it is extracted from *Cleome gynandra* L. (Capparidaceae). It is equally effective to reduce OS by suppressing superoxide radical, hydroxyl radical and NO in the isolated peripheral blood mononuclear lymphocytes of cases with RA and human erythrocytes. Allylpyrocatechol (APC; 3-prop-2-enylbenzene-1,2-diol): it is isolated from Piper betle (Family-Piperaceae) (4, 45, 46). The effect of APC on nitric oxide calculated in macrophages using 4,5-diaminofluorescein diacetate by flow cytometry whereas, it reduced synthesis of nitric oxide in synovial infiltrated cells. The effect also associated with its in vitro nitric oxide scavenging function. Curcumin: curcumin is yellow hydrophobic polyphenol compound extracted from the herb turmeric. It is effective through somatostatin production via cAMP/ PKA and Ca²⁺/CaMKII signaling mechanisms. However, “thetracurmin” which is a highly bioavailable form of curcumin, is detected effective in cases with osteoarthritis to decrease pain. Curcumin analogue Diarylpentanoid (BDMC33): it significantly suppresses the progelatinase B (pro-MMP-9) and collagenase functions via inhibition of MMP-1 in activated SF. Furthermore, BDMC33 strongly inhibited MMP-3 gene expression as well as suppressed COX-2 and IL-6 gene expression. BDMC33 inhibit the p65 NF- κ B nuclear translocation and NF- κ B DNA binding function in PMA-stimulated SF. Epigallocatechin-3-gallate: green tea polyphenol Epigallocatechin-3-gallate regulates inducible nitric oxide synthase (45, 46). It also suppresses IL-1 β - induced phosphorylation and proteasomal degradation of I κ B α to inhibit NF- κ B nuclear translocation. Genistein: isoflavones such as genistein and daidzein are detected in different plants including lupin, fava beans, soybeans, kudzu, and psoralea. It is also detected as the primary food source in the medicinal plants like *Flemingia vestita*, *F. macrophylla*, and coffee. Genistein suppresses mediators or growth factor-induced production and transformation phenotype in fibroblast-like synoviocytes in RA. Icaritin: *Epimedium herba* is one of the most commonly investigated herbs for treatment of bone metabolic and related disorders in China (45, 47, 48). *Epimedium* flavonoid is composed of seven flavonoid compounds and its main active compound extracted as Icaritin. Icaritin increases bone-healing. Icaritin has the potential for increasing bone formation via its osteo-promotive but not an osteo-inductive process. Paeoniflorin: total glycosides of paeony (TGP) are extracted from *Radix paeoniae*, in which paeoniflorin is the major active compound (45-47, 49). TGP/paeoniflorin inhibit inflammatory mechanism by decreasing the synthesis of prostaglandin E₂, leukotriene B₄, nitric oxide, ROS, proinflammatory mediators and chemokines. TGP/paeoniflorin also suppresses the production

of lymphocytes and fibroblast-like sinoviocytes. The inhibitory roles in formation of new blood vessels, and the synthesis of matrix metalloproteinase is also revealed. Plants provide a rich resource for natural drug investigation and development. In recent years, the application of traditional medicine evidence on plant investigations received notable interest. Furthermore, the more use of dietary antioxidants is continuously increasing worldwide. The recent investigations focused on the scientific and clinical pathogenesis of RA in association with OS and the effectiveness of the plant-derived active compounds on all type of inflammatory cells is demonstrated (17, 47, 49).

6. Crohn's Disease

6.1. Pathophysiology of Crohn's Disease

Crohn's disease (CD) is a debilitating disease of the bowel known by chronic inflammation of unknown pathophysiology. In the United States and Europe, the incidence ranges from 6-20 cases per 100000 population per year, and the prevalence, from 90-300 per 100000 population. The exact etiology of CD remains unknown. It seems that interactions among different factors, including genetic factors, host immune system and environmental factors (including diets and microbiological agents), play pivotal roles in impairing the intestinal homeostasis, causing the dysregulated inflammatory responses of the gut (50, 51). As inflammation is intimately associated to the formation of reactive intermediates, including ROS, OS has been suggested as a process underlying the pathophysiology of CD. The main pathological characteristic of CD is an infiltration of polymorphonuclear neutrophils and mononuclear cells into the affected part of the intestine (7, 50). As the disease becomes more known, neutrophils infiltrate isolated crypts, creating abscesses in the affected mucosa and underlying tissue layers. Neutrophils, like other leukocytes, secrete noxious substances, such as ROS, tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF α), interleukin-1 (IL-1) and protease. It has been revealed that an imbalance in the levels of proinflammatory and anti-inflammatory mediators occurs in CD. Higher levels of proinflammatory mediators, such as IL-1, IL-8 and TNF α , can be found in CD. ROS may play a significant role in CD. The ROS generated from activated leukocytes or from other sources may affect different biological molecules, producing tissue damage that could have been prevented by dietary antioxidants (50, 51).

6.2. Antioxidants and Crohn's Disease

An antioxidant is any substance or compound that removes oxygen free radicals or suppresses the oxidation mechanism in the cell. The level of antioxidant defenses available within the cells and extracellularly should be appropriate to oppose the toxic effects of lipid peroxides and to maintain normal physiology. This balance can be lost due to the over-synthesis of free radicals or the inadequate consumption of nutrients containing antioxidant molecules. Antioxidants can be noted as plasma antioxidants and intracellular antioxidants. The main role of plasma antioxidant defense is to bind transition metal ions, such as iron and copper, thereby reducing their plasma level and capacity to trigger free radical mechanisms (52, 53). This prevents the production of hydroxyl radicals of the very potent variety that is able to produce lipid peroxides. This is provided by plasma antioxidants, such as transferrin, lactoferrin, ceruloplasmin, albumin, uric acid, haptoglobins, and hemopexin. Ascorbic acid is also a plasma antioxidant

that can remove water-soluble peroxy radicals and other ROS. This is accomplished through the completion of two mechanisms. First, the ascorbic acid is converted into the ascorbyl radical and then to dehydroascorbate. Ascorbic acid can also decrease α -tocopheryl radicals to α -tocopherol at the cell membrane surface. Vitamin E (α tocopherol), a lipid peroxidation, chain-breaking antioxidant, is found in membranes and lipoproteins. It is the most significant lipid-soluble antioxidant in the human plasma. Vitamin E commonly donates a hydrogen atom to the peroxy radical and prevents the propagation of the chain process of lipid peroxidation (52, 54). Each tocopherol can react with two $\text{LOO}\cdot$, the first $\text{LOO}\cdot$ reacts with α -tocopherol to form the α -tocopherol radical that reacts with the second $\text{LOO}\cdot$ to make a stable adduct ($\text{LOO-}\alpha$ -tocopherol). Reduced blood and mucosal levels of vitamins A, C, E and β -carotene were shown in Crohn's patients. It has been reported that antioxidants suppressed the synthesis of inflammatory mediators, such as IL-1 and $\text{TNF}\alpha$, in the colonic mucosa of inflammatory bowel disease cases. Vitamin C and E suppressed the levels of OS in human intestinal smooth muscle (HISM) cells isolated from Crohn's bowels (53). The most important intracellular antioxidant enzymes are superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione peroxidase (GSHPx), and catalase. Human plasma has very little or no catalase, but it has low functions of SOD and GSHPx. SOD is localized in both the cytosol (CuZn-SOD) and the mitochondria and has role to dismutate superoxides into hydrogen peroxide and molecular oxygen. SOD is known as the main intracellular enzyme due to it can reduce the most abundant free radical, $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$. Catalase reacts rapidly with hydrogen peroxide, a precursor of $\cdot\text{OH}$ in the existence of iron, and converts it into water and molecular oxygen. Selenium glutathione peroxidase also converts hydrogen peroxide into water and lipid hydroperoxides into water and harmless fatty acid alcohols. Low intestinal mucosal levels of CuZn superoxide dismutase and glutathione were shown in Crohn's cases (52-55).

7. Conclusion

Several studies propose that OS might be involved in the pathogenesis of autoimmune diseases, and that antioxidant consumption may be effective in management and treatment of these diseases. However, very few clinical investigations have been carried out to show whether antioxidant intake may effectively protect or slow down the progression of the autoimmune diseases. To determine efficacy in slowing down the progression of autoimmune diseases, the candidate antioxidants must be given as early as possible, before cell damages and irreversible impairments. It also should be tailored to the exact OS mechanisms including the type of ROS involved, the place of production, and the severity of the impairments. Furthermore, the investigated antioxidant should be able to penetrate into the site of damage following systemic consumption in order to achieve an appropriate therapeutic level. Therefore, antioxidant cocktails or those combined with the other common treatments of autoimmune diseases such as immunosuppressors or immunomodulator drugs, may have more successful synergistic roles. Well-designed clinical investigations using antioxidant administration, as well as observational studies based on larger cohort studies, over a longer duration of the study, are required in order to assess whether antioxidant administration may be effective for treatment of autoimmune diseases.

Declarations

Acknowledgement

The author thanks all those who contributed to this study.

Author Contribution

Fatemeh Taheri: Study design, review of literature, writing draft of study.

Funding/Support

No funding was provided for this study.

Conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study.

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